

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TRANSLATIONS OF THE NOVEL “THE
BEAD GAME” BY H. HESSE

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Annotation: Today, we have a number of classifications, which, although they have common features, still differ. The reason for this is that the topic of equivalence and methods of equivalent translation has only a few decades. There is currently no single definition of equivalent and equivalence accepted by all scientists.

Key words: classification, equivalence and methods, translation, substitution, correspondences, alternative.

In the practical part of my work, I propose to analyze for the presence and difference or coincidence of translation correspondences two translations of one passage from the famous German novel by Hermann Hesse “The Glass Bead Game”.

- Die geistige Bewegung...

The beginning of a spiritual movement ... is a direct (simple) substitution.

The ideological current ... is a complex alternative substitution.

Both methods are possible in my opinion.

- Die geistige Bewegung...

The beginning of a spiritual movement ... is a direct (simple) substitution.

The ideological current ... is a complex alternative substitution.

Both methods are possible in my opinion.

•... deren Fruchte unter vielen anderen die Einrichtung des Ordens und das Glasperlenspiel sind...

- ... leading, in particular, to the establishment of the Order and to the game of glass beads ... - a complex alternative substitution.

... whose consequences include the founding of the Order and the Glass Bead Game ... - an ordinary substitution.

The usual substitution method seems to me to be a priority for maintaining greater equivalence between the original and the translation.

- ...deren Fruchte unter vielen anderen die Einrichtung des Ordens und das Glasperlenspiel sind...

... leading, in particular, to the establishment of the Order and to the game of glass beads ... - a complex alternative substitution.

... the consequences of which include the founding of the Order and the Glass Bead Game ... - an omission according to L.S. Barkhudarov and A. Burak.

The method of complex alternative substitution seems to me more suitable for maintaining greater equivalence between the original and the translation.

- ...deren Fruchte unter vielen anderen die Einrichtung des Ordens und das Glasperlenspiel sind.

... leading, in particular, to the establishment of the Order and to the game of glass beads ... - a complex alternative substitution.

...whose consequences include the founding of the Order and the Glass Bead Game... a complex alternative substitution.

Both methods are possible in my opinion.

- Die geistige Bewegung ... hat ihre Anfänge in einer Geschichtsperiode.

The beginning of a spiritual movement ... refers to a period of history - a complex alternative substitution.

The ideological current ... originates in that historical period - a simple (direct) substitution.

The method of direct (simple) substitution seems to me more suitable for maintaining greater equivalence between the original and the translation.

Both methods are possible in my opinion.

- Solche Namen sind hubsch...

Such labels are beautiful... - direct (simple) substitution.

Names like these are tempting... a complex alternative substitution. Both methods are possible in my opinion.

- Solche Namen sind hubsch...

Such names are seductive ... - a simple (direct) substitution.

The method of direct (simple) substitution seems to me to be a priority for maintaining greater equivalence between the original and the translation.

- Solche Namen sind hubsch...

Such labels are beautiful... - simple (direct) substitution.

Names like these are tempting... a complex alternative substitution. The method of direct (simple) substitution seems to me more suitable for maintaining greater equivalence between the original and the translation.

After analyzing several examples of translators choosing different types of substitutions, we can conclude that the method of complex alternative substitution is the most commonly used. Similarly, the simple/direct substitution method is quite often used by translators in order to maintain greater equivalence between the original text and the target text, but in cases where the translator needs to translate some phraseological phrase, cliché or cliché, it is preferable to use the usual substitution method.

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